

Run-time motion and first-order shim control by expanded servo navigation

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Abstract

Purpose: To provide a navigator-based run-time motion and first-order field correction for 3D human brain imaging with high precision, minimal calibration and acquisition, and fast processing.

Methods: A complex-valued linear perturbation model with feedback control is extended to estimate and correct for gradient shim fields using orbital navigators (2.3 ms). Two approaches for sensitizing the model to gradient fields are presented, one based on finite differences with three additional navigators, and another projection-based approximation requiring no additional navigators. A mechanism for noise decorrelation of the matrix and the data is proposed and evaluated to reduce unwanted parameter biases.

Results: The rigid motion and first-order field control achieves robust motion and gradient shim corrections improving image quality in a series of phantom and in-vivo experiments with varying field conditions. In phantom scans, magnet drifts, forced gradient field perturbations and field distortions from shifts of a second bottle phantom are successfully corrected. Field estimates of the magnet drifts are in good agreement with concurrent field probe measurements. For in-vivo scans, the proposed method mitigates field variations from torso motions while being robust to head motion. In-vivo gradient field precisions were 30 nT/m along with single-digit micrometer and millidegree rigid precisions.

Conclusion: The navigator-based method achieves accurate, high-precision run-time motion and field corrections with low sequence impact and calibration requirements.

Keywords: field correction, head motion, motion correction, orbital navigators, linear regression, feedback control

Introduction

Signal instabilities from motion and field dynamics paired with the long acquisition times of MRI are limiting factors in many clinical and research applications (1). For human brain imaging, head motion is a major cause of signal inconsistencies (2; 3; 4) often requiring costly rescans (5). For that reason, head motion has been targeted by a wide range of sensing mechanisms including external sensors (6; 7; 8; 9), MR navigators (10; 11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19; 20; 21) and data consistency driven approaches (22; 23; 24; 25; 26) for the use in prospective and retrospective correction schemes.

Besides head motion, magnetic field variations are another major cause of dynamic signal changes that especially affect imaging with long echo times, long readouts, and at high-field (27; 28; 29). Field fluctuations relevant to head imaging arise from magnet drifts and other hardware imperfections (30; 31), chest and limb motion (32; 33), and changes in head pose, which also alter susceptibility-induced fields (34; 35). Known field fluctuations can be addressed at the reconstruction level. However, this option is limited to relatively small fluctuations that do not impair conditioning and is computationally demanding particularly in the presence of higher-order fluctuations (36). For best efficiency of image encoding and ease of reconstruction it is preferable to counter field excursions by run-time shim adjustments (37).

The joint correction of head motion and shim fields has been addressed by several methods in the literature. The cloverleaf navigator (14) proved effective for run-time rigid and first-order field corrections, which, however, requires a 12s calibration scan that is assumed motion-free. The FID navigator approach has been shown to address rigid motion (19) and shim fields (38) in retrospect and also run-time shim adjustments (39). This method, however, requires a separate low-resolution pre-scan for calibration. Retrospective corrections also increase the computational reconstruction load and are vulnerable to Nyquist violations. SENSE shimming (40) investigated shim field corrections based on coil arrays and navigator projections, but requires a low-resolution pre-scan and is lacking integration with a rigid correction technique.

Liu et al. presented a retrospective method based on two segmented 3D-EPI navigators in the sequence, covering not only rigid and shim field corrections but also coil sensitivity and pose-dependent field variations (20), but this comes with long navigator acquisitions, and the mentioned downsides of retrospective techniques. In contrast to navigator methods, Vionnet et al. proposed a run-time rigid motion and shim field correction based on field probe sensing (41; 42; 43) that provides precise parameter estimates, albeit requiring complex instrumentation and relying on a

rigid relation of the probes to the skull.

This work expands the recently published servo navigator method for run-time rigid and zeroth-order field control (21) to first-order shim control. This is achieved by extending the underlying complex-valued linear perturbation model by signal derivatives with respect to first-order background fields. The additional derivatives are determined either by minimal reference acquisition or in a projection-based reference-less fashion. Along with the shim expansion, this work studies bias in fitted motion and field parameters and describes a strategy of removing such bias by avoiding noise correlation between the left- and right-hand sides of the signal model. A series of phantom and in-vivo experiments is conducted to evaluate the proposed method for various types of field perturbations. The field correction accuracy is evaluated with respect to field probe measurements in phantom scans.

Methods

Linear signal model

The proposed method relies on navigator acquisitions for rigid motion and field tracking with coil arrays and volume excitation. For this, an orbital navigator (21), which acquires three orthogonal orbits at a k-space radius of 400 rad/m in 2.3 ms, is inserted in a 3D gradient-echo sequence as shown in Supporting Figure S1. The method can also handle other trajectories including spheres (13) and Lissajous (18). A linear model is calibrated in a fraction of a second on-the-fly at the start of the sequence. Then, parameter updates are continuously estimated and used for scan geometry and shim updates forming a control loop that keeps the model valid beyond the initial linear regime.

The variation of the complex-valued navigator signal \vec{s} is modeled by linear expansion using Taylor's theorem around an initial reference navigator signal $\vec{s}^{(0)}$ with respect to a set of dynamic parameters $\vec{\Delta}$ as proposed in Ref. (21). The matrix M is consequently formed by the derivatives of the signal with respect to the parameters in $\vec{\Delta}$:

$$\vec{s}(\vec{\Delta}) - \vec{s}^{(0)} = M\vec{\Delta}. \quad [1]$$

The vector $\vec{\Delta}$ comprises three rotation angles $(\Delta\alpha, \Delta\beta, \Delta\gamma)$, and three shifts $(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)$, a global phase offset $\Delta\phi$ and a global frequency offset $\Delta\omega$. This work extends the servo navigator method (21) by three gradient field offsets $(\Delta G_x, \Delta G_y, \Delta G_z)$ for the gradient fields in scan geometry

coordinates, i.e. frequency, phase, and slice encoding direction, yielding $n_\Delta = 11$ parameters:

$$\vec{\Delta} = (\Delta\alpha, \Delta\beta, \Delta\gamma, \Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z, \Delta\phi, \Delta\omega, \Delta G_x, \Delta G_y, \Delta G_z)^T. \quad [2]$$

The linear model requires the determination of the matrix columns in M comprising the signal derivatives with respect to the model parameters. Let matrix M comprise $n_\Delta = 11$ columns and $n_c \cdot n_\tau$ rows, where c and τ count the n_c and n_τ total coils and navigator samples. The matrix entry of coil c and sample τ in column one is denoted $M_{(c,\tau),1}$. The signal derivatives with respect to rotations, shifts, global phase and global frequency follow the descriptions of Ref. (21) and are briefly summarized in Supporting Information S1. Rotational derivatives are determined by finite differences in this work.

Signal derivatives with respect to gradient fields

Finite differences

The signal derivatives with respect to gradient fields in matrix columns $M_{(c,\tau),9-11}$ can be determined using finite differences:

$$M_{(c,\tau),9} = \frac{1}{\delta G} \left(s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0,\Delta G_x)} - s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0)} \right) \quad [3]$$

$$M_{(c,\tau),10} = \frac{1}{\delta G} \left(s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0,\Delta G_y)} - s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0)} \right) \quad [4]$$

$$M_{(c,\tau),11} = \frac{1}{\delta G} \left(s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0,\Delta G_z)} - s_{(c,\tau)}^{(0)} \right). \quad [5]$$

To this end, three further reference navigators $\vec{s}^{(0,\Delta G_x)}$, $\vec{s}^{(0,\Delta G_y)}$, and $\vec{s}^{(0,\Delta G_z)}$ are acquired initially in subsequent TRs similar to Ref. (44), each in the presence of a shim of amplitude δG in, respectively, the frequency, phase, and slice encoding direction. The finite differences approach is visualized in Supporting Figure S1. $\delta G = 5 \mu\text{T/m}$ was chosen as a trade-off between the linear range discussed below and the navigator SNR.

Projection-based approximation

As an alternative, a projection-based approximation can be used to determine the signal derivatives with respect to gradient fields requiring no extra reference navigators to set up the matrix M . The approach is similar to the rotational derivative approximation in Ref. (21). The k-space content $\sigma_c(\vec{k}, \vec{\Delta}, t)$ of coil c at k-space location \vec{k} is described with respect to its initial reference state $\sigma_c^{(0)}(\vec{k})$:

$$\sigma_c(\vec{k}, \vec{\Delta}, t) = \sigma_c^{(0)} \left(R(\vec{\Delta})\vec{k} + \Delta\vec{k}_G \right) \exp \left(i\vec{k}^T \Delta\vec{r} \right) \exp \left(i\Delta\phi + i\Delta\omega t \right), \quad [6]$$

with rotation matrix $R(\vec{\Delta})$ built from the rotations $(\Delta\alpha, \Delta\beta, \Delta\gamma)$, the shift vector $\Delta\vec{r} = (\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)^T$ and the k-space shift $\Delta\vec{k}_G$ caused by a gradient field offset $\Delta\vec{G} = (\Delta G_x, \Delta G_y, \Delta G_z)^T$.

Then, its derivative with respect to ΔG_x at $\vec{\Delta} = 0$ is

$$\left. \frac{\partial \sigma_c(\vec{k}, \vec{\Delta}, t)}{\partial \Delta G_x} \right|_{\vec{\Delta}=0} = \vec{\nabla}_k \left(\sigma_c^{(0)}(\vec{k}) \right)^T \left(\left. \frac{\partial (\Delta\vec{k}_G)}{\partial \Delta G_x} \right|_{\vec{\Delta}=0} \right). \quad [7]$$

Although the reference navigator with its limited k-space support has insufficient information for the full derivative of $\sigma_c^{(0)}(\vec{k})$, it still contains the signal change along the trajectory direction. This component is extracted by substituting the derivative in brackets by its projection onto the temporal derivative of \vec{k} :

$$proj_{\dot{\vec{k}}} \left(\left. \frac{\partial (\Delta\vec{k}_G)}{\partial \Delta G_x} \right|_{\vec{\Delta}=0} \right) = \frac{\dot{\vec{k}}(t)}{\|\dot{\vec{k}}(t)\|^2} \left(\dot{\vec{k}}(t)^T \left. \frac{\partial (\Delta\vec{k}_G)}{\partial \Delta G_x} \right|_{\vec{\Delta}=0} \right). \quad [8]$$

Modeling the k-space shift to be caused by a gradient field offset that is constant over TR gives $\Delta\vec{k}_G(t) = 2\pi \gamma_{1H} \Delta\vec{G}t$ with the sampling time t , and the gyromagnetic ratio γ_{1H} . Its derivative with respect to ΔG_x is simply $2\pi \gamma_{1H} t \vec{e}_x$ with the unit vector \vec{e}_x . Using the same replacements as Eqs. 10-12 in Ref. (21):

$$s_c(t, \vec{\Delta}) = \sigma_c(\vec{k}(t), \vec{\Delta}, t) \quad [9]$$

$$s_c^{(0)}(t) = \sigma_c^{(0)}(\vec{k}(t)) \quad [10]$$

$$\dot{s}_c^{(0)}(t) = \vec{\nabla}_k \left(\sigma_c^{(0)}(\vec{k}(t)) \right)^T \dot{\vec{k}}(t), \quad [11]$$

the navigators signal change with respect to the gradient shim offset ΔG_x can be approximated as:

$$\left. \frac{\partial s_c(t, \vec{\Delta})}{\partial \Delta G_x} \right|_{\vec{\Delta}=0} \approx \frac{\dot{s}_c^{(0)}(t)}{\|\dot{\vec{k}}(t)\|^2} \left(2\pi \gamma_{1H} t \dot{k}_x(t) \right), \quad [12]$$

where $\dot{k}_x(t) = \dot{\vec{k}}(t)^T \vec{e}_x$. The navigator signal derivatives with respect to ΔG_y and ΔG_z can be derived analogously. These three equations can be used to approximate the matrix columns 9-11 of M replacing Eqs. 3-5.

As for the rotational derivatives, the projection approach neglects signal change orthogonal to the trajectory direction producing errors in the matrix. The propagation of these incoherent errors into the parameter estimates is reduced by the overdetermination of the multi-coil navigator sampling. Furthermore, Ref. (21) showed that, for closed-loop control and linear conditions, errors in the matrix can be tolerable affecting convergence but not necessarily the fix point of convergence.

Parameter estimation

To ensure the parameter estimates are real-valued, the matrix formulation is split into real and imaginary parts denoted by $\Re(\cdot)$ and $\Im(\cdot)$. The parameter estimate $\vec{\Delta}'$ is calculated by the linear least-squares solution (21):

$$\vec{\Delta}' = \left(\begin{pmatrix} \Re(M) \\ \Im(M) \end{pmatrix}^H \begin{pmatrix} \Re(M) \\ \Im(M) \end{pmatrix} \right)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \Re(M) \\ \Im(M) \end{pmatrix}^H \begin{pmatrix} \Re(\vec{s} - \vec{s}^{(0)}) \\ \Im(\vec{s} - \vec{s}^{(0)}) \end{pmatrix}, \quad [13]$$

with the matrix M and signal vectors \vec{s} and $\vec{s}^{(0)}$ of the current and the reference navigator, respectively. The matrix needs to have full rank for successful parameter estimation and yields optimal precision considering complex zero-mean Gaussian noise. If the latter condition is not met, pre-whitening can be applied for decorrelation and uniform variance (45).

The calculations involved can be separated into an initial calculation of the pseudo-inverse and its application. In the first step, the $(n_\Delta \times 2n_c n_\tau)$ pseudo-inverse is determined including few matrix multiplications and an inversion of a $n_\Delta \times n_\Delta$ (here: 11×11) matrix. The second parameter estimation step applies the pseudo-inverse to the current navigator signal difference using $2n_\Delta n_c n_\tau$ multiplications and additions and can be performed in run-time on current machines for practical n_c and n_τ .

Linear range

The linear range in which the first-order approximation of the signal model is sufficiently accurate is a crucial measure for robust parameter control. Ref. (21) provides rough approximations of the linear ranges with respect to shifts, rotations, global phase and global frequency offsets. An approximation of the linear range for gradient field offsets can be derived similarly, considering that k-space content consists of plane waves $e^{i\vec{k}(t) \cdot \vec{r}}$ with $\|\vec{r}\|$ up to $\text{FOV}/2$ for a spherical object with that radius. A gradient offset $\Delta\vec{G}$ assumed constant over a TR leads to a trajectory deviation $\Delta\vec{k}(t) = 2\pi\gamma_{1H} \Delta\vec{G}t$. Given $\|\vec{r}_{max}\| = \text{FOV}/2$, the related phase shift along a plane wave is at most $\pi\gamma_{1H} t\text{FOV}\|\Delta\vec{G}\|$. Assuming linear approximations of trigonometric functions to be sufficiently accurate below, e.g., 0.2 rad, an estimate of the linear range can be established. For $\text{FOV} = 0.2 \text{ m}$ and a maximum navigator sampling time $t_{max} = 3 \text{ ms}$, the estimate is $\|\Delta\vec{G}\| < \frac{0.2 \text{ rad}}{\pi \gamma_{1H} t_{max} \text{FOV}} \approx 2.5 \frac{\mu\text{T}}{\text{m}}$.

Servo control including gradient shims

Servo control is based on tracking the current system state of scan geometry and shim field conditions under which a navigator has been acquired along with the navigator. From that, the parameter update and the new system state is calculated. Updates of scan geometry, global phase and frequency offsets are performed as described in Ref. (21). Adopting the same notation, the left-multiplying rotation matrix $R_{total,j}$ of repetition j transforms from scan coordinates (x, y, z) with frequency, phase, and slice encoding direction to magnet coordinates $(\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z})$, $\Delta\vec{r}_{total,j}$ describes the off-center in magnet coordinates, and $\Delta\phi_{total,j}$ and $\Delta\omega_{total,j}$ describe the global phase and frequency offsets, respectively. This work adds the gradient shim offset $\Delta\vec{G}_{total,j} = (\Delta G_{total,\hat{x}}, \Delta G_{total,\hat{y}}, \Delta G_{total,\hat{z}})^T$ in magnet coordinates. The parameters are initialized by zero for $j = 0$, apart from the rotation matrix $R_{total,0}$ which is set to the initial scan angulation.

The scan geometry, phase and shim field updates are then performed as follows:

$$R_{total,j} = R_{total,j-1} R(\Delta\alpha_j, \Delta\beta_j, \Delta\gamma_j) \quad [14]$$

$$\Delta\vec{r}_{total,j} = \Delta\vec{r}_{total,j-1} + R_{total,j} \Delta\vec{r}_j \quad [15]$$

$$\Delta\phi_{total,j} = \Delta\phi_{total,j-1} + \Delta\phi_j \quad [16]$$

$$\Delta\vec{G}_{total,j} = \Delta\vec{G}_{total,j-1} - R_{total,j} \Delta\vec{G}_j \quad [17]$$

$$\Delta\omega_{total,j} = \Delta\omega_{total,j-1} + (\Delta\omega_j + R_{total,j} \Delta\vec{G}_j \cdot \Delta\vec{r}_{total,j}). \quad [18]$$

where $\Delta\vec{r}_j = (\Delta x_j, \Delta y_j, \Delta z_j)^T$ is the current shift update and $\Delta\vec{G}_j = (\Delta G_{x,j}, \Delta G_{y,j}, \Delta G_{z,j})^T$ the current gradient shim update in iteration j , both in scan geometry coordinates. Shim parameters determined in off-isocenter scan coordinates require a translation correction to transform the estimates into the magnet coordinate frame. For first-order shimming, Eq. 18 contains the shim-induced global field change $\Delta\omega_{ind,j} = R_{total,j} \Delta\vec{G}_j \cdot \Delta\vec{r}_{total,j}$.

In this notation, the gradient shim changes are subtracted, because the parameters are actively actuated, i.e. the estimated gradient field needs to be counteracted. In contrast, the global field $\Delta\omega_{total,j}$ is compensated in the demodulation process requiring accumulation at this stage instead of subtraction.

A major benefit of scan geometry and shim field control is that sampling inconsistencies, such as Nyquist violations from rotations or undetected field gradients, can be mitigated in run-time, while image reconstruction times are kept the same (2). In addition, the run-time updates stabilize the linear parameter estimation, as the working point of the linearization effectively follows the motion

and field conditions. By this, the linear range estimated above becomes only a limitation per update cycle (few TRs) allowing for larger motion excursion with linear modeling.

Noise decorrelation by additional reference navigator

A closer look into Eq. 13 reveals that the reference navigator with its inherent noise vector $\vec{\eta}^{(0)}$ is both present in the matrix M and in the rightmost data vector. The columns of matrix M are built from scaled versions of the reference noise vector $\vec{\eta}^{(0)}$, while the data vector contains $\vec{\eta}^{(0)}$ through the navigator difference. Thus, the right-most matrix-vector product in Eq. 13 comprises the scalar product of $\vec{\eta}^{(0)}$ with itself. Having a positive expectation value, this product introduces bias that spreads into all model parameters via the inverse of the model matrix.

As the reference noise vector is kept the same over the whole scan, this parameter offset remains time-stable and appears from the first estimation. It thus leads to a consistent but slightly shifted stable point of the control process. The biases can be avoided by acquiring the baseline reference navigator twice, once to build the model matrix and once for the left-hand side of the linear model (Eq. 1). Noise is then uncorrelated between the two sides, removing the biases. In the following, this second reference option is used unless stated otherwise.

Data acquisition and reconstruction

A series of navigated 3D gradient echo scans was performed in a phantom and in-vivo to evaluate the performance of the proposed run-time method. Four volunteers were scanned in accordance with the local ethical regulations. The scans were conducted on a 3T Philips Achieva scanner with a 16-channel Skope Neurocam head coil including 16 field probes for concurrent field monitoring. A list of relevant scan parameters is provided in Tab. 1. For the phantom scans, a spherical phantom described in Ref. (21) was used, which is filled with doped water and PMMA balls providing internal structure for the motion experiments. A linear 3D Cartesian sampling order was chosen for all scans. Throughout, shimming was performed using vendor-provided volumetric shimming. For image reconstruction, the vendor’s SENSE implementation was used.

The proposed PMC method with run-time first-order shim estimation and actuation is termed *PMC 1*. For reference, it is compared to the previously published run-time PMC method with zeroth-order shim control (21) denominated *PMC 0*. For both *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* it is possible to disable any geometry and field updates during the scan, so that motion and field parameters are estimated but not updated. *PMC off* refers to *PMC 0* without updating.

Phantom experiments

Long-term stability

High-resolution phantom scans were conducted to investigate the long-term behavior of the proposed run-time method. The 24-min scan was repeated for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* both with and without run-time updates. In addition, concurrent field monitoring was used to obtain time-resolved third-order harmonic field expansions of every tenth navigator readout.

Comparison with field probe measurements

The concurrent field monitoring data is used as a reference to independently evaluate the accuracy of the navigator-based field estimates, i.e. the global frequency offsets $\Delta\omega_{total,j}$ and the gradient shim offsets $\Delta\vec{G}_{total,j}$. For this comparison, the field monitoring data requires several processing steps. First, third-order spherical harmonic functions are fitted to the monitored field probe phase data (46). Second, the fitted zeroth- and first-order trajectories are extracted and cropped to the navigator acquisition duration. Third, a field monitoring readout is selected that corresponds to the reference navigator signal. Fourth, trajectory deviations are determined by subtracting the reference trajectory from all others. Finally, the zeroth- and first-order field terms are extracted as the slopes of temporal first-order fits of the trajectory deviations. By this, B_0 and gradient field estimates are obtained for each navigator readout from the high temporal resolution field probe data resembling the overall field characteristics the navigator senses.

Bias mitigation by additional reference

To show the effect of the additional reference for noise decorrelation, a set of 3-min phantom 3D GRE scans was performed for both *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* with and without the additional reference.

Step response to perturbations

The control and convergence behavior of the proposed method was characterized by forced perturbations of the scan geometry and shims played out by the scanner. More specifically, scan geometry offsets of 2 mm and 2° , f_0 offsets of 10 Hz and gradient field offsets of $10 \frac{\mu\text{T}}{\text{m}}$ were sequentially introduced each 200th TR (every 8 seconds). Each perturbation was set and held for 10 TRs for full settling. Then, the control mechanism was enabled to counteract the perturbation. Phase and slice encoding were switched off to achieve a steady-state with equal conditions for all perturbations.

Note that these first-order field perturbations are introduced by the same coils that the method is correcting with and the system can, thus, return to exactly the initial conditions.

Field perturbation by bottle shift

To study the system response to field changes due to in-bore sources and not restricted to first order, a 5l water bottle was placed on the patient bed in the vicinity of the spherical phantom. The bottle's top was initially placed 15 cm from the phantom and manually shifted towards it by 10 cm, at half scan time (after 1 min). This time point corresponds to the k-space center sampling, for which image quality is expected to be most vulnerable (35). This scan was performed with and without bottle motion for *PMC off*, *PMC 0*, *PMC 1* with the default finite differences approach, and *PMC 1* with the projection-based approximation to determine signal derivative with respect to gradient fields.

In-vivo experiments

Four volunteers were scanned for *PMC off*, *PMC 0*, and *PMC 1* with three motion scenarios. First, the volunteers were asked to remain still (no instructed motion). Second, the volunteers were asked to move the right arm from the hip to the left shoulder at half scan time and hold the position until the end of the scan. Third, the volunteers were asked to perform a combined nodding and head shake rotation in the range of up to 2 degrees at half scan time and hold the position. Motion instructions were indicated by light signals and the order of the PMC types was randomized and unknown to the volunteers. The experiments thus represent no intended perturbations (no motion), field perturbations from sources outside the FOV (arm motion), and mixed field and rigid perturbations including field variations from internal sources.

nRMSE metrics were calculated on magnitude images after affine registration using the *PMC off* data without instructed motion as a reference. A cross-subject nRMSE analysis is shown in Supporting Figure S2. Note that these values need to be interpreted with care due to potential motion corruption of the reference itself and pose-dependent inter-scan contrast variations that appear even for ideal intra-scan motion correction.

Results

Phantom experiments

Long-term stability

Figure 1 shows the resulting high-resolution images and the respective parameter time courses of *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. The image of *PMC off* is provided for reference along with close-ups to allow image quality comparisons of small structures. In the following, the plots show the total parameters with respect to the reference and the Δ in the parameter names is dropped for improved legibility.

The resulting images of the three methods show no considerable difference in image quality yielding comparable fine-structure details in the close-ups. The rotation, shift, and global phase (ϕ_0) parameters stay in the range of 30 mdeg, 20 μm , and 1 deg for both methods. *PMC 1* detected a larger f_0 drift in its scan than *PMC 0*. After about 15 min, f_0 is plateauing and a $\Delta G_{total,\hat{x}}$ gradient field drift to $-0.7 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$ is detected and compensated for *PMC 1*. The model residuals are close to each other. Table 2 lists parameter precisions for relevant scans, which were estimated from the upper half of the parameter spectra (above 6 Hz) assuming drifts and motion to be mainly present below that cut-off frequency.

While the rigid parameters are expected to remain zero for the phantom, the magnetic field is subject to drift effects as, for example, from heating processes of the gradient coils and other parts. Taking into account changes of the magnet conditions, the parameters must be compared cautiously between the long scans. Concurrent field probe measurements are thus used for reference.

Comparison to field probe measurements

Figure 2 compares the field estimates of the field probes and the navigator for the long-term stability scans for both *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b). The f_0 traces generally coincide well for both methods. The field probes achieve high f_0 precisions. Note that f_0 is not actuated but handled in the demodulation process and both sensing mechanisms should therefore obtain the same f_0 traces.

In contrast, the gradient shim offsets are estimated and actuated in run-time for *PMC 1*. As the field probes sense the superposition of the external field drift with the actuated shims, *PMC 1* presents a successful field compensation in Fig. 2b achieving a flat, stabilized trace with drifts below 200 nT/m as seen by the field probes. This amounts to residual k-space shifts below 3.4% of a Nyquist interval for $\text{FOV} = 0.2 \text{ m}$ and $T_E = 20 \text{ ms}$. The absolute drift range for *PMC 1* which

had to counteract field drifts, was even lower than for *PMC 0*, which was free, by chance, from significant gradient field drifts.

The long-term stability scans have been re-scanned without phase encoding to evaluate the impact of the phase encoding gradients onto the parameter estimates, which is shown in Supporting Figures S3 and S4. In this case, both scans were subject to similar gradient field drifts leading to larger rigid parameter drifts and model residuals for *PMC 0*, while *PMC 1* effectively mitigates the field changes. The parameter variations are dominated by the field drifts, while the impact of the phase encoding gradients onto the parameter traces is much more subtle.

Bias mitigation by additional reference

Figure 3 shows the comparison of the parameter traces for *PMC 1* with and without additional reference for noise decorrelation. In the top row with only one reference, the rotations, shifts, and gradient shims contain small initial offsets of approx. 20 mdeg, 10 μm , and 0.4 $\mu\text{T}/\text{m}$, which remain present over the whole scan leading to a slight geometry and field offset with respect to the intended reference conditions. These offsets can be largely mitigated using the second reference option shown in the bottom row. Supporting Figure S5 confirms this effect for *PMC 0*.

Step response to perturbations

Figure 4 shows the settling behavior for *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b) with forced gradient shim perturbations. For *PMC 0*, the undetected field conditions introduce rigid parameter biases of up to 0.25 mm and deg and f_0 biases of up to 15 Hz. In contrast, *PMC 1* senses and actuates the shim field perturbations stabilizing the system to precision levels again within a fraction of a second. Supporting Figure S6 shows an extended version adding the parameter responses to frequency and rigid perturbations. *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* perform quite similarly detecting and counteracting the perturbations in a fraction of a second returning to deviations on the precision levels.

Field perturbation by bottle shift

Figure 5 compares the performance of the different PMC methods for field perturbations from shifts of a second phantom bottle outside the FOV. *PMC off* shows strong image artifacts introduced by the bottle shifts, which are consistently reduced with increasing field order. The run-time first-order corrections by *PMC 1* appear to be well suited to compensate the present field perturbations, the

required order of correction nevertheless depends on the exact arrangement and sequence parameters. The f_0 traces agree well between *PMC 0* and both *PMC 1* methods. Minor time shifts of the perturbation probably stem from slight deviations in the reproduction of the manual bottle shifts. Both *PMC 1* methods counteracted gradient field variations of about $2 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$ in $\Delta G_{total,\hat{x}}$ and $\Delta G_{total,\hat{z}}$, and, by that, reduced the model residual of the parameter fits by similar factors. The projection-based *PMC 1* method, which requires no additional reference navigators, obtains similar image quality and reduces precision by at most a factor of three (Tab. 2) compared to the finite differences approach.

In-vivo experiments

No instructed motion

Figure 6 shows the in-vivo imaging results without instructed motion, which provide comparable image quality. In the *PMC 1* parameter traces, breathing patterns are clearly captured in rigid and field parameters. The center plot compares the z shift after high-pass filtering, which was applied with a cut-off frequency of 0.8 Hz to reduce breathing-induced variations, with the pulse oximeter signal for a zoomed time frame. The shift spikes, which probably stem from cardioballistic effects on the head, coincide well with the signal peaks from the pulse oximeter. The parameter trace spectra on the right confirm the presence of breathing-related frequencies in all parameters, while cardiac-related frequencies can only be differentiated from the noise floor for the rigid parameters.

The additional modeling and actuation of gradient shims for *PMC 1* leads to comparable image quality and similarly depicts physiology as *PMC 0* from Ref. (21). The estimated gradient shim parameters contain breathing-related patterns as observed in previous studies (43), especially dominant in foot-head direction (33). An overview of the reconstructed images from all subjects is given in Supporting Figure S7.

Instructed arm motion

Figure 7 shows the in-vivo imaging results for instructed arm motion. Introducing a field perturbation from a source outside the FOV, *PMC off* shows strong shading artifacts that are increasingly mitigated with rising field correction order. Residual artifacts may persist due to the presence of higher-order field components and field correction latencies, which were about 4-5 TRs on the current system as for the rigid corrections in Ref. (21). Nevertheless, the image quality improvements

of *PMC 1* underline the benefits of the proposed method for run-time gradient updates in-vivo. Supporting Figure S8 provides an extension of Fig. 7 showing breathing patterns and continuous motion drifts over the scan as well as involuntary head motion triggered by the instructed arm motion. An overview of the reconstructed images from all subjects is given in Supporting Figure S9.

Instructed head motion

Figure 8 compares the imaging results from two subjects for instructed head motion. The movement introduces strong blurring artifacts and field-related signal dropouts for *PMC off*, which are effectively reduced by *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. *PMC 1* further mitigates some minor artifacts at the frontal lobe above the nasal cavities. The motion and field parameters of Subject 1 for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* show comparable rigid excursions of 2 deg and 2 mm as well as a frequency step of about 5 Hz. For this case, *PMC 1* detected and corrected an anterior-posterior gradient field step $\Delta G_{total,\hat{y}}$ of $1.5 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$.

The head motion event presents a combined motion and field disturbance with field components from internal sources like the nasal cavities and distant sources due to the relative motion of the head with respect to the chest. The spatially complex field changes from internal sources are beyond the capacity of the proposed model, but have been shown to make up for a large proportion of the motion-induced field changes (35). Nevertheless, *PMC 1* shows no increased vulnerability towards these unmodeled effects and still consistently improves image quality. It is noteworthy that the first-order field corrections, although being globally beneficial over the whole brain, can locally deteriorate image quality. If there is, for example, a quadratic field component in anterior-posterior direction, a first-order correction could improve the frontal lobe while deteriorating the occipital lobe. An overview of the reconstructed images from all subjects is given in Supporting Figure S10.

Discussion

According to these results, servo navigation with expansion to first-order shim control is an effective means of jointly handling motion and field fluctuations. Combining complex-valued linear regression with continuous feedback, it reconciles high precision with little run-time computation and minimal calibration requirements. In this work, the proposed method achieved gradient field precisions below 30 nT/m and maintains the single-digit micrometer and millidegree rigid precisions of the previous

method while still relying on short orbital navigators with 2.3 ms duration. The finite differences approach for determining signal derivatives with respect to gradient fields requires three additional navigator acquisitions (three extra TRs). Alternatively, a projection-based approach for derivative determination achieved competitive precisions without extra reference data. Successful run-time corrections have been confirmed by concurrent field probe measurements in phantom scans, while the method provides high sensitivity to physiology data in-vivo.

Precision

The precision of global frequency offsets was below 0.28 (0.23) Hz and the gradient field precision was below 30 (22) nT/m for in-vivo (phantom) imaging. These precision levels even revealed subtle magnetic field drifts (Fig. 1), probably caused by dynamics of the gradient cooling during the scan, and in-vivo physiology related to breathing and cardiac function (Fig. 6). Breathing belt measurements showed high correlations of rigid, global frequency and gradient field parameter traces with the respiratory cycle. The importance of such field corrections, esp. for high-field imaging, has been described in previous studies (33; 43; 37; 42). In-vivo precisions were found to remain largely unaffected by motion staying at similar values after a motion event (Tab. 2).

Navigator acquisition within few ms after excitation was found to offer adequate field precision for imaging with substantially longer TE and thus greater sensitivity to field offsets. For still higher field sensitivity the navigator duration can be increased. Precision may prove insufficient with very short navigators and long echo times or readout durations. In this case, field precision can be boosted at the expense of temporal resolution by low-pass filtering.

The projection-based determination of derivatives with respect to gradient fields, which requires no extra reference data, reduced the gradient shim precision by up to a factor of 3 with respect to the finite differences approach. This probably reflects slightly slower controller convergence due to model error incurred by projection as previously discussed in Ref. (21). It could partly relate also to some deterioration of the conditioning of the model matrix.

Accuracy

We distinguish multiple conditions of field and motion perturbations for which accuracy is evaluated. By fitting first-order spherical harmonics, the method is especially well suited for field perturbations from sources distant to the imaging FOV. This includes, for example, the adverse effects of magnet drifts, breathing and torso motions, but not necessarily of head motion (35). Thus, a separation

with respect to the type of field perturbation is necessary.

For the long-term stability phantom scans, passive and unintended magnet drifts were observed and corrected by the first-order shim control. As a quantitative assessment, the method achieved accuracies below 200 nT/m using concurrent field monitoring as reference. The step response and bottle shift experiments represented active first-order and low-order field perturbations, respectively, for which artifacts were effectively mitigated. For the step response scans, the method returned to errors on the precision level within a fraction of a second. The experiments further indicated that undetected gradient shim fields of $10\ \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$ can introduce substantial rigid parameter biases of up to 0.25 deg and mm for such navigator methods that were successfully reduced with gradient shim control. For the bottle shift and in-vivo experiments, image quality improvements serve as an indicator for accuracy.

Secondary motion effects

Accompanying the primary gross motion, MR signal consistency is affected by secondary motion effects, such as pose-dependent magnetic field and coil sensitivity variations (2). With head motion, field variations from sources internal or close to the FOV play an important role (35), which explains why increasing the corrected field order in this study hardly improves image quality or nRMSE for instructed head motion cases. While still providing robust gross motion correction, the proposed method lacks, as expected, modeling power for pose-dependent field changes, which are not captured well by a basis of gradient fields and by harmonic functions in general (35). There are attempts to address these field variations with dedicated coil arrays trying to approximate common field distributions (27; 29). Another approach is to correct for these field variations retrospectively (47).

The benefits and challenges of array detection for the proposed method have been discussed in Ref. (21). The proposed method greatly benefits from the data redundancy provided by coil arrays yielding high parameter precisions. Nevertheless, the coil sensitivity weighting of an anatomy changes with motion (23). These unmodeled variations accumulate for large motion excursions and can lead to biases in the parameter estimates. The integration of secondary motion effects like pose-dependent coil sensitivity and higher-order field variations for large motion remain subject to future research. With this challenge remaining, servo navigation with shim control is promising particularly for high resolution imaging of cooperative volunteers.

Optional decoupling of navigator and image corrections

Effects like eddy currents or mechanic system oscillations may violate the assumption that navigator estimates describe the conditions of the imaging signal well, which could hinder the use of navigator corrections. Still, the first-order field corrections would improve the signal consistency for the navigator itself. In some cases, it could therefore be beneficial to decouple the navigator from the image corrections. Instead of adjusting the overall shim settings in run-time, the navigator trajectory could be continuously adapted during the scan, by including the gradient shim changes as trajectory shifts for each navigator time point. In this way, the navigator can estimate rigid motion parameters accounting for field changes up to first order, while the imaging scan is left unaffected by the run-time shim changes.

Sequence considerations

The proposed method is currently restricted to 3D sequences with constant contrast. The model does not naturally extend to 3D motion estimation for 2D sequences as discussed in Ref. (21). For contrast variations, recent work starts using low-resolution quantitative MRI to trace signal evolution with varying contrast (48), which is, however, currently not run-time feasible. For sequences like MPRAGE with varying contrast within an echo train, it is possible to adapt the proposed method using the property that the contrast is still constant between echo trains. For this, multiple reference navigators can be acquired over the echo train to calibrate multiple models at different contrast stages for motion estimation.

Advances in shimming technology

Dynamic shimming is currently an active field of research (27; 28; 29; 37) fueled by the growing interest in high-field imaging. The fast, on-point switching of shim coils is, however, limited by coupling and cross-talk among the coils and with the magnet. Hardware and methodological advances including active shielding, coil decoupling and shim pre-emphasis (49) can alleviate these limitations in the future. Furthermore, the development of matrix shim arrays with different spatial basis sets (29) open up new opportunities for the dynamic shimming of pose-dependent field variations. The finite differences approach for shim-related derivatives used in this work enables the integration of any shim coil by measuring the induced navigator signal changes and adapting the control loop. In this way, advances in methods and scanner hardware accelerate the performance of run-time rigid

motion and shim field corrections.

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References

- [1] Van Der Kouwe A, Andre JB *Motion Correction in MR: Correction of Position, Motion, and Dynamic Field Changes*. Academic Press; 2022.
- [2] Maclaren J, Herbst M, Speck O, Zaitsev M. Prospective motion correction in brain imaging: A review. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2013;69(3):621–636.
- [3] Zaitsev M, Maclaren J, Herbst M. Motion artifacts in MRI: A complex problem with many partial solutions: Motion Artifacts and Correction. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*. 2015;42(4):887–901.
- [4] Godenschweger F, Kägebein U, Stucht D, et al. Motion correction in MRI of the brain. *Physics in Medicine and Biology*. 2016;61(5):R32–R56.
- [5] Andre JB, Bresnahan BW., Mossa-Basha M, et al. Toward Quantifying the Prevalence, Severity, and Cost Associated With Patient Motion During Clinical MR Examinations. *Journal of the American College of Radiology*. 2015;12(7):689–695.
- [6] Zaitsev M, Dold C, Sakas G, Hennig J, Speck O. Magnetic resonance imaging of freely moving objects: prospective real-time motion correction using an external optical motion tracking system. *NeuroImage*. 2006;31(3):1038–1050.
- [7] Ooi MB, Krueger S, Thomas WJ, Swaminathan SV, Brown TR. Prospective real-time correction for arbitrary head motion using active markers. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2009;62(4):943–954.

- [8] Schildknecht CM, Brunner DO, Schmid T, Reber J, Marjanovic J, Pruessmann KP. Wireless motion tracking with short-wave radiofrequency. *Proceedings of the 27th International Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine, Montreal, Canada*. 2019;27:66.
- [9] Niekerk A, Van Der Kouwe A, Meintjes E. Toward “plug and play” prospective motion correction for MRI by combining observations of the time varying gradient and static vector fields. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2019;82(3):1214–1228.
- [10] Ehman RL, Felmlee JP. Adaptive technique for high-definition MR imaging of moving structures.. *Radiology*. 1989;173(1):255–263.
- [11] Fu ZW, Wang Y, Grimm RC, et al. Orbital navigator echoes for motion measurements in magnetic resonance imaging. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 1995;34(5):746–753.
- [12] Ward HA, Riederer SJ, Grimm RC, Ehman RL, Felmlee JP, Jack CR. Prospective multiaxial motion correction for fMRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2000;43(3):459–469.
- [13] Welch EB, Manduca A, Grimm RC, Ward HA, Jack Jr. CR. Spherical navigator echoes for full 3D rigid body motion measurement in MRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2002;47(1):32–41.
- [14] Van Der Kouwe A, Benner T, Dale AM. Real-time rigid body motion correction and shimming using cloverleaf navigators. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2006;56(5):1019–1032.
- [15] White N, Roddey C, Shankaranarayanan A, et al. PROMO: Real-time prospective motion correction in MRI using image-based tracking. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2010;63(1):91–105.
- [16] Kober T, Marques JP, Gruetter R, Krueger G. Head motion detection using FID navigators. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2011;66(1):135–143.
- [17] Skare S, Hartwig A, Mårtensson M, Avventi E, Engström M. Properties of a 2D fat navigator for prospective image domain correction of nodding motion in brain MRI: 2D FatNav for Motion Correction in Brain MRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2015;73(3):1110–1119.
- [18] Buschbeck RP, Yun SD, Jon Shah N. 3D rigid-body motion information from spherical Lissajous navigators at small k-space radii: A proof of concept. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2019;82(4):1462–1470.

- [19] Wallace TE, Afacan O, Waszak M, Kober T, Warfield SK. Head motion measurement and correction using FID navigators. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2019;81(1):258–274.
- [20] Liu J, Gelderen P, Zwart JA, Duyn JH. Reducing motion sensitivity in 3D high-resolution T2*-weighted MRI by navigator-based motion and nonlinear magnetic field correction. *NeuroImage*. 2020;206:116332.
- [21] Ulrich T, Riedel M, Pruessmann KP. Servo navigators: Linear regression and feedback control for rigid-body motion correction. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2024;91(5):1876–1892.
- [22] Atkinson D, Hill DLG, Stoye PNR, Summers PE, Keevil SF. An autofocus algorithm for the automatic correction of motion artifacts in MR images. In: Duncan James, Gindi Gene, Goos Gerhard, Hartmanis Juris, Leeuwen Jan, eds. *Information Processing in Medical Imaging*, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg 1997 (pp. 341–354).
- [23] Bammer R, Aksoy M, Liu C. Augmented generalized SENSE reconstruction to correct for rigid body motion. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2007;57(1):90–102.
- [24] Loktyushin A, Nickisch H, Pohmann R, Schölkopf B. Blind retrospective motion correction of MR images: Blind Retrospective Motion Correction. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2013;70(6):1608–1618.
- [25] Haskell MW, Cauley SF, Bilgic B, et al. Network Accelerated Motion Estimation and Reduction (NAMER): Convolutional neural network guided retrospective motion correction using a separable motion model. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2019;82(4):1452–1461.
- [26] Polak D, Splitthoff DN, Clifford B, et al. Scout accelerated motion estimation and reduction (SAMER). *Magnetic resonance in medicine*. 2022;87(1):163–178.
- [27] Koch KM, Rothman DL, De Graaf RA. Optimization of static magnetic field homogeneity in the human and animal brain in vivo. *Progress in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy*. 2009;54(2):69–96.
- [28] Juchem C, De Graaf RA. B₀ magnetic field homogeneity and shimming for in vivo magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *Analytical Biochemistry*. 2017;529:17–29.
- [29] Stockmann JP, Wald LL. In vivo B₀ field shimming methods for MRI at 7 T. *NeuroImage*. 2018;168:71–87.

- [30] Boesch C, Gruetter R, Martin E. Temporal and spatial analysis of fields generated by eddy currents in superconducting magnets: Optimization of corrections and quantitative characterization of magnet/gradient systems. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 1991;20(2):268–284.
- [31] Vannesjo SJ, Haeberlin M, Kasper L, et al. Gradient system characterization by impulse response measurements with a dynamic field camera. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2013;69(2):583–593.
- [32] Raj D, Paley DP, Anderson AW, Kennan RP, Gore JC. A model for susceptibility artefacts from respiration in functional echo-planar magnetic resonance imaging. *Physics in Medicine and Biology*. 2000;45(12):3809–3820.
- [33] Moortele P, Pfeuffer J, Glover GH, Ugurbil K, Hu X. Respiration-induced B0 fluctuations and their spatial distribution in the human brain at 7 Tesla. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2002;47(5):888–895.
- [34] Marques JP, Bowtell R. Application of a Fourier-based method for rapid calculation of field inhomogeneity due to spatial variation of magnetic susceptibility. *Concepts in Magnetic Resonance Part B: Magnetic Resonance Engineering*. 2005;25B(1):65–78.
- [35] Liu J, Zwart JA, Gelderen P, Murphy-Boesch J, Duyn JH. Effect of head motion on MRI B₀ field distribution: Liu et al.. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2018;80(6):2538–2548.
- [36] Wilm BJ, Barmet C, Pavan M, Pruessmann KP. Higher order reconstruction for MRI in the presence of spatiotemporal field perturbations: Higher Order Reconstruction for MRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2011;65(6):1690–1701.
- [37] Gelderen P, De Zwart JA, Starewicz P, Hinks RS, Duyn JH. Real-time shimming to compensate for respiration-induced B0 fluctuations. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2007;57(2):362–368.
- [38] Wallace TE, Afacan O, Kober T, Warfield SK. Rapid measurement and correction of spatiotemporal B₀ field changes using FID navigators and a multi-channel reference image. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2020;83(2):575–589.
- [39] Wallace TE, Kober T, Stockmann JP, Polimeni JR, Warfield SK, Afacan O. Real-time shimming with FID navigators. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2022;88(6):2548–2563.

- [40] Splitthoff DN, Zaitsev M. SENSE shimming (SSH): A fast approach for determining B_0 field inhomogeneities using sensitivity coding: SENSE Shimming (SSH). *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2009;62(5):1319–1325.
- [41] Haeberlin M, Kasper L, Barmet C, et al. Real-time motion correction using gradient tones and head-mounted NMR field probes. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2015;74(3):647–660.
- [42] Duerst Y, Wilm BJ, Wyss M, et al. Utility of real-time field control in T_2^* -Weighted head MRI at 7T: Utility of Real-Time Field Control. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2016;76(2):430–439.
- [43] Vionnet L, Aranovitch A, Duerst Y, et al. Simultaneous feedback control for joint field and motion correction in brain MRI. *NeuroImage*. 2021;226:117286.
- [44] Splitthoff DN, Zaitsev M. Theoretical basis of projection based shim estimation. *Proceedings of the 19th annual meeting of the ISMRM, Montreal, Canada*. 2011;Abstract no. 0285.
- [45] Pruessmann KP, Weiger M, Börnert P, Boesiger P. Advances in sensitivity encoding with arbitrary k-space trajectories. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2001;46(4):638–651.
- [46] Barmet C, De Zanche N, Pruessmann KP. Spatiotemporal magnetic field monitoring for MR. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2008;60(1):187–197.
- [47] Brackenier Y, Cordero-Grande L, Tomi-Tricot R, et al. Data-driven motion-corrected brain MRI incorporating pose-dependent B_0 fields. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2022;88(2):817–831.
- [48] Brackenier Y, Wang N, Liao C, et al. Rapid and accurate navigators for motion and B_0 tracking using QUEEN: Quantitatively enhanced parameter estimation from navigators. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2024;91(5):2028–2043.
- [49] Vannesjo SJ, Duerst Y, Vionnet L, et al. Gradient and shim pre-emphasis by inversion of a linear time-invariant system model: Gradient and Shim Pre-emphasis by Inversion of an LTI Model. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2017;78(4):1607–1622.

Tables

Table 1: Scan parameters for phantom and in-vivo navigated 3D gradient echo imaging scans. FOV: field of view, FA: Flip angle, $R_p \times R_s$: Reduction factors in phase and slice encoding direction.

Experiment		Figs.	FOV mm ³	Resolution mm ³	T_E ms	T_R ms	FA °	$R_p \times R_s$	Time mm:ss
Long-term stability	Phantom	1-2	180x180x80	0.4x0.4x1.0	12	40	5	1×1	24:00
Additional reference	Phantom	3	180x180x100	1.0x1.0x2.0	14	40	5	2×1	03:01
Step response	Phantom	4	180x180x100	1.0x1.0x2.0	14	40	5	2×1	03:01
Shift of 2nd bottle	Phantom	5	190x190x100	0.8x0.8x4.0	21	40	5	2×1	01:58
No/arm/head motion	In-vivo	6-8	220x220x100	0.8x0.8x2.5	20	36	5	1.5×1.5	03:00

Table 2: Precisions for phantom and in-vivo scans without active perturbations. Precisions are calculated from the parameter spectra above 6 Hz to exclude slow drifts and motion. For the experiments termed motion of 2nd bottle, the precisions were estimated for the first third of the scan before the bottle shift. For in-vivo head motion, precisions are estimated for the time after the motion event. FD: Finite differences approach; PR: projection-based approach.

Experiment	Method	α	β	γ	x	y	z	ϕ	$\omega/(2\pi)$	$G\hat{x}$	$G\hat{y}$	$G\hat{z}$
		mdeg			μm			deg	Hz	nT/m		
Long-term stability (Phantom)	PMC 0	1.39	1.44	0.99	1.34	1.37	1.72	0.24	0.19	8.03	7.76	19.17
	PMC 1 FD	1.42	1.47	0.98	1.35	1.38	1.73	0.25	0.18			
Shift of 2nd bottle (Phantom)	PMC 0	1.59	1.45	1.23	1.62	1.79	2.06	0.23	0.24	9.54	9.24	21.33
	PMC 1 FD	1.57	1.54	1.21	1.69	1.73	2.11	0.21	0.23			
	PMC 1 PR	1.77	1.48	1.27	1.76	1.83	2.2	0.24	0.24			
No motion (In-vivo)	PMC 0	4.79	2.94	3.98	3.19	4.16	5.66	0.25	0.28	22.50	23.94	29.06
	PMC 1 FD	5.33	3.51	4.91	3.17	5.64	4.95	0.26	0.28			
Head motion (In-vivo)	PMC 0	4.90	2.91	4.18	3.93	6.19	4.45	0.25	0.28	24.23	25.81	25.75
	PMC 1 FD	4.34	3.15	5.29	3.27	5.63	4.51	0.23	0.29			

Figures

Figure 1: Long-term stability phantom scans for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. The left plot shows the resulting images for *PMC 0*, *PMC 1* and *PMC off*. Close-ups are drawn from the white boxes. The run-time adjusted parameter traces are displayed for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* next to the images in the same row. The residuals of the linear fits are shown in the upper-right. The methods achieve comparable image quality and similarly small rigid parameter and phase drifts over the 24-minute scans. The accuracy of the field evolution is investigated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of field estimates based on field probes and navigators. The zeroth- and first-order field estimates are compared for both *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b). The f_0 traces correspond well for both methods. For *PMC 0*, the gradient shims were not fitted in the navigator model, while the field probes detect slight drifts below $0.2 \mu\text{T/m}$. For *PMC 1*, the navigator-based gradient shims were updated in run-time and show a $\Delta G_{total, \hat{x}}$ field evolution to $-0.7 \mu\text{T/m}$. As this field course was successfully counteracted in run-time, the probes do not detect this detrimental effect yielding stabilized gradient fields.

Figure 3: Additional reference navigator to avoid initial parameter offsets for *PMC 1*. Parameter traces over the 3-min scan course with two referencing options for the calculation of the matrix and the data side. (Top row) One reference navigator for both operations (*One reference*). (Bottom row) A separate navigator for each of the two operations (*Two references*). The initial parameter offsets that are visible especially for rotations and gradient shims are largely mitigated when using the second reference navigator.

Figure 4: Step response experiments for *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b). Each column contains the system response to the gradient shim perturbations stated above the column. Row 1: Current scan geometry. Row 2: Current phase and field parameters. Black horizontal lines indicate the target value of the perturbed parameter. Row 3: Difference from target value Δ_i for parameter index i normalized by precisions σ_i . *PMC 0* is incapable to address the gradient shim perturbations producing offsets in the other parameters, while *PMC 1* mitigates the disturbance in a fraction of a second. The responses to rigid and frequency perturbations are given along with the precisions in Supporting Figure S6.

Figure 5: Field perturbations from shift of a second bottle phantom at half scan time. The top row shows reconstructed images and close-ups for the different PMC settings, comparing also the finite differences and projection-based approach to determine derivatives with respect to gradient fields. In the rows below, the field parameter and model residual traces for the two methods are shown in direct comparison with $PMC\ 0$. The image artifacts consistently decrease with increasing field correction order. Both $PMC\ 1$ methods achieve similar field estimates.

Figure 6: In-vivo results without voluntary motion. Top row: Transversal and sagittal images for *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* with (white) nRMSE values. The methods achieve similar image quality. Bottom row: The left plot shows four rigid and field parameter traces of *PMC 1* compared to breathing belt and pulse oximeter signals. The parameter variations are strongly correlated with the breathing cycle. The frequency ω is converted to $B_0 = \omega / (2\pi\gamma_{1H})$. The center plot highlights the correspondence of the peaks from the high-pass filtered z shifts with the cardiac cycle (pulse oximeter). The right tile shows the parameter spectra with prominent frequency bands for respiratory and cardiac activity.

Figure 7: In-vivo results with arm motion at half scan time. Top row: Transversal, sagittal and zoom images for *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* with (white) nRMSE values. The arm motion during the scan results in strong image artifacts for *PMC off*, which are reduced for *PMC 0* and largely mitigated for *PMC 1* supported also by nRMSE improvements. Bottom row: Field parameter traces and model residual for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. The arm motion event at half scan time is clearly visible. *PMC 0* estimates only f_0 a strong increase in the model residual. *PMC 1* additionally models gradient shims, which results in a different estimate for f_0 and achieves model fit residuals much closer to initial conditions. The f_0 difference between *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* arises from the fact that undetected gradient fields are misinterpreted as f_0 components for off-center imaging.

Figure 8: In-vivo imaging with head motion at half scan time. Top row: Transversal and sagittal images for *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* with (white) nRMSE values. The blurring from the head motion for *PMC off* is largely mitigated by *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* with no clear preference in nRMSE between the two. Bottom rows: Rigid and field parameter plots for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* showing comparable rotations, shifts and f_0 traces. *PMC 1* further detected and actuated a gradient shim offset of $1.5 \mu\text{T/m}$ in \hat{y} direction. Head motion introduces strong field variations with considerable contribution of components beyond the first-order field model. Still *PMC 1* provides robust rigid motion and first-order field corrections.

Supporting Figures

Figure S1: 3D GRE sequence with orbital navigator and finite differences approach. (a) Gradient pulse sequence in frequency (F), phase (P) and slice (S) direction along with RF excitation and acquisition. The finite differences method for determining signal derivatives with respect to gradient fields is indicated in colors. One additional navigator is acquired for each of the three directions, for which the respective gradient shim is switched on during the TR. (b) The scan procedure starts with 100 dummy cycles to build up the longitudinal steady state of the spoiled gradient echo sequence. Then, one to eight navigators are acquired for setting up the system matrix depending on the choice of derivative determination.

Figure S2: Cross-subject nRMSE analysis of the in-vivo data from four subjects. Boxplots (a) for the ‘no motion’ (left), ‘arm motion’ (center), and ‘head motion’ (right). *PMC off* with ‘no motion’ is the reference giving zero values. For ‘arm motion’, *PMC 1* clearly outperforms *PMC 0* and *PMC off*, while *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* show similar performance for ‘no motion’ and ‘head motion’. The images (b) show examples for arm and head motion with the reference (left) and magnitude differences to the reference (other). For arm motion, there is a clear reduction of field-related signal drop-out from *PMC off* to *PMC 1* (orange arrows). For head motion, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* show fewer anatomical features in the difference due to the successful motion correction. The signal voids above the nasal cavities (red arrows) are, however, a pose-dependent characteristic of each scan on its own complicating nRMSE comparisons to the reference in-vivo despite effective intra-scan motion correction.

Figure S3: Long-term stability phantom scans for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* without phase encoding. The run-time adjusted parameter traces are displayed for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* in rows 2 and 3, respectively. The residuals of the linear fits are shown in the upper-right. Images are not available due to absence of phase encoding. *PMC 0* shows larger drifts in the rigid parameters and model residuals than *PMC 1*, which corrected for clearly visible gradient field drifts. The accuracy of the field evolution is investigated in Supporting Figure S4.

Figure S4: Comparison of field estimates based on field probes and navigators for long-term stability scans without phase encoding. The zeroth- and first-order field estimates are compared for both *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b). The f_0 traces correspond well for both methods. For *PMC 0*, the gradient shims were not fitted in the navigator model, while the field probes detect variations of up to $0.6 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$. For *PMC 1*, the navigator-based gradient shims were updated in run-time and show a similar field evolution with up to $-0.7 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$. As this field course was successfully compensated in run-time, the probes do not detect this detrimental effect yielding stabilized gradient fields with variations below $0.2 \mu\text{T}/\text{m}$.

Figure S5: Additional reference navigator to avoid initial parameter offsets for *PMC 0*. Parameter traces over the 3-min scan course with two reference options for the calculation of the matrix and the data side. (Top row) One reference navigator for both operations (*One reference*). (Bottom row) A separate navigator for each of the two operations (*Two references*). The initial parameter offsets that are visible for rotations and shifts are largely mitigated using the second reference navigator. Gradient shims are not estimated by *PMC 0*.

Figure S6: Step response experiments for *PMC 0* (a) and *PMC 1* (b) including rigid, frequency and gradient shim perturbations. Each column contains the system response to the perturbation stated above the column. Row 1: Current scan geometry. Row 2: Current phase and field parameters. Black horizontal lines indicate the target value of the perturbed parameter. Row 3: Difference from target value Δ_i for parameter index i normalized by precisions σ_i printed in the third column to equalize the scales. Both *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* achieve similar accuracy and precisions for rotations (α shown), shifts (x shown) and f_0 . For gradient field steps, *PMC 0* is incapable to address the perturbations producing offsets in the other parameters, while *PMC 1* mitigates the disturbance in a fraction of a second.

Figure S7: In-vivo scan overview without instructed motion. Each row shows the images of one subject for the three methods *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. Every transversal-sagittal image pair represents a separate scan. The tiled overview should give an impression of the methods' performance over all subjects. All three methods obtain comparable image quality for all subjects.

Figure S8: A variation of Fig. 7 in the manuscript showing: (a) images with nRMSE values. (b) motion and field parameters including also the respiratory belt data (black curve) for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. (c) Close-ups of the parameter traces in Response Figure 1 for the time range from 30-60 seconds. The L2-norm of the shifts and rotations over time are plotted, respectively, for legibility of the rigid motion data. The L2-norm rotations contain components around the right-left (RL) and the anterior-posterior (AP) axis. Breathing patterns and continuous motion drifts can be observed as well as involuntary head motion coming along with the instructed arm motion.

Figure S9: In-vivo scan overview with instructed arm motion at half scan time. Each row shows the images of one subject for the three methods *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. Every transversal-sagittal image pair represents a separate scan. The volunteers were instructed to reproduce the motion as good as possible. The tiled overview should give an impression of the methods' performance over all subjects. For all four subjects, *PMC off* presents strong image shading artifacts, which are slightly improved by *PMC 0*. *PMC 1* outperforms the other two methods largely mitigating the arm motion-induced image artifacts by run-time gradient field actuation.

Figure S10: In-vivo scan overview with instructed head motion at half scan time. Each row shows the images of one subject for the three methods *PMC off*, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. Every transversal-sagittal image pair represents a separate scan. The volunteers were instructed to reproduce the motion as good as possible. The tiled overview should give an impression of the methods' performance over all subjects. *PMC off* overall shows increased motion-induced blurring artifacts that are reduced for *PMC 0* and *PMC 1*. As the field variations from head motion are insufficiently captured by a first-order field model, *PMC 0* and *PMC 1* perform similarly. Nevertheless, the methods remain stable despite the unmodeled field effects.